

DIFFICULTIES IN ENTERING THE EU MARKET FOR AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS**Natia Daghelishvili***Prof., Grigol Robakidze University, Georgia***Tamar Gamsakhurdia***Prof., rigol Robakidze University, Georgia***Mikheil Tabatadze***Master in Business Administration**GSG, Georgia***Abstract**

Diversification of exports and deepening of trade relations is a constant concern of any country. This issue becomes especially relevant if the preferential regime provides an opportunity for economic integration. The Association Agreement (AA) and the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) between Georgia and the European Union have offered the possibility of economic integration into the EU single market since 2014. Since export diversification is found in the agricultural sector in the top ten export goods both by commodity and geography, and the sector is monopolized or oligopolized according to the main export products, the article will focus on the difficulties of entering the EU market for agricultural products, and more precisely on the role and importance of small agrolistics centers. Based on the results of the research, the article presents conclusions about what should be the optimal agrolistics center for the reality of Georgia, which includes all links of the value chain of agricultural products production.

Keywords: Agricultural products, free trade, Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA), entry into the EU single market, tariff and non-tariff barriers, agro-logistics centers.

Introduction

Georgia is highly dependent on the Russian market from the traditional big markets, although the country is in the process of searching for alternative markets. This process is facilitated by the Association Agreement (AA) between Georgia and the European Union and its trade component - the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA).

Due to the high political risks of the Russian market, it is vital for Georgia from an economic point of view to use the preferences of the deep and comprehensive free trade trade space with the European Union, which is the basis of economic integration with the European Union, however there are also free trade agreement between Georgia and some other global players (Wang et al. 2018; Lashkhi, Charaia 2020; 2021; Papava, Charaia, 2017). There is no alternative to the single market of the European Union due to its scale and the purchasing power of the population, its gross domestic product per capita is 42,450 US dollars as of 2021. It is the largest global player in terms of GDP and volume of investments. Nevertheless, exports to the European Union will account for 10-15% of the total exports of the country, according to the indicators of the last 3 years. Dependence on the Russian market is increasing, in 2021, compared to 2020, the export of Georgian products to Russia increased by 38% and reached 610 million US dollars. In the Russian market, ferroalloys took the first place in exports with 172 million US dollars. Wine has a high share of 55% in the export of agricultural products. The share of agriculture in GDP is 7% (Geostat, 2022).

The main categories of goods exported to the EU single market are raw materials, namely ore and copper concentrates, fertilizers, petroleum products and ethyl alcohol (Daghelishvili, 2016). Accordingly, these are

the sectors that are mostly monopolized and oligopolized (Sikharulidze, Charaia, 2018). Nuts (HS 0802) and wine (HS 2204) are among the ten products exported from the agricultural sector to the EU single market, whose share in total exports is quite low. From the agricultural sector, non-tariff barriers have been overcome so far in these areas and a competitive product has been offered on the EU market, although the continuous supply of a uniform product remains a challenge.

In recent years, considerable financial and not only financial resources have been spent on the development of agriculture in Georgia, and some progress has been observed in terms of modernization of the field, increase in yield, and improvement of quality infrastructure, although there is still a long way to go to the desired goal including creation of the stable financial environment, with stable inflation and exchange rate parameters (Charaia, Papava, 2019; 2020; 2021; 2022). First of all, it is worth noting the non-compliance with EU standards and the faulty production chain, to which is added the issue of raising farmers' awareness, which the Ministry of Environment Protection and Agriculture has been working on for several years through various projects and programs (through agricultural information-advisory services and extension centers). However, a certain part of farmers prefers the traditionally established Russian market to try to enter the EU single market.

As a result of the implementation of the trade component of the Association Agreement (DCFTA) in 2014, it was expected that the trade in Georgian agricultural products in the EU would increase dramatically and thus the country's economy would receive significant benefits (Case, Ecorys, 2012). The Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement provides for exemp-

tion from customs duties on the import of goods originating in Georgia to the European Union. Despite the given preference, the export of goods of Georgian origin, including agricultural products, to EU countries did not increase as much as it was expected. The European Union market is particularly focused on the protection of consumer rights, the consumer is more demanding, which turned out to be an obstacle for Georgian agricultural products to enter the European market, because the local products were significantly inferior to the products placed on the European Union market, both in terms of quality indicators and production scale. That is why in the 2015-2020 and 2021-2027 strategies, special emphasis is placed on bringing the requirements and technical parameters of Georgian agricultural products closer to the requirements of the European Union market, the practical implementation of which is impossible without effective agrologistics centers.

Review of scientific literature

A key aspect for the development of the agricultural sector and the creation of a rural economy is the regulation of supply chain management and logistics lines in the agrarian sector. Systemic management solutions needed to solve the difficulties faced by agrologistics are offered by the "agribusiness value chain", where the model of functioning of an effective agrologistics system is as follows:

- Farmers should be encouraged by expanding support to associations, consortia, cooperatives and self-help groups, which will increase the effective use of resources;
- Means of marketing of agricultural products should be improved (Abashidze, 2016);
- Processing centers must become more efficient;
- effective and targeted agricultural policy development;
- A relevant storage system with efficient refrigeration facilities should be created;
- Transport should be widely developed, especially in rural areas;
- Financial system should be stable, including local currency exchange rate (Anguridze et al., 2015; Gamsakhurdia et al., 2017; Gamsakhurdia, Fetelava, 2023; Tsutskiridze, 2023);
- Professional education and professional orientation should play a significant role (Kvirkvaia et al., 2018; Zivzivadze et al., 2021);
- The shortage of electricity should be eliminated through non-traditional sources of electricity production, such as solar, wind, etc. and (Chandrasekaran, Raghuram, 2014).

In addition, the focus is on the role of government in agribusiness supply chain development. The World Bank's article "Agro-Logistics in Central America" (World Bank, 2012), describes the state of agro-logistics markets in the countries of Central America and the Caribbean.

A comparison of large and small farmers involved in livestock production in this region, specifically in beef production, shows the importance of economies of scale and a high level of infrastructure in rural areas for

maximizing trade benefits, especially in case of fintech sector development (Charaia et al., 2021; Lashkhi, 2022; Lashkhi et al., 2022). As a result of the mentioned comparison, it can be seen that where the logistics infrastructure is in order, the farmer's costs per unit of production are much less, therefore the benefits obtained as a result of trade are greater. And the logistics infrastructure is more organized in the region where relatively large farmers gather.

In the classical sense, an agro-logistic center is a unit created for a certain geographical area, within which activities related to transportation, logistics and distribution of goods or raw materials are carried out by different operators on a commercial basis (Kiladze, 2017). Operators can be owners or tenants of buildings (warehouses, distribution centers, storage areas, offices, truck services, etc.). The logistics center should be provided with an information-consulting service. In order to facilitate the international intermodal movement of goods, it is desirable that the logistics center has access to land, rail, sea, inland water and air transport. To ensure synergy and commercial cooperation, it is important that the logistics center is managed by a single and neutral legal entity (preferably a public-private partnership). If we apply the existing classical definition to the agronomic field and consider agricultural products instead of goods, raw materials for planting, and agricultural machinery instead of equipment, or machines used in this field, then we will automatically be connected to the agrologistics center.

In the article "Agro-industrial supply chain management: concepts and applications" (Vorst, Silva, Trienekens, 2007) published by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations FAO, based on research by Wageningen University on the importance of agro-logistics centers in developing economies, the authors emphasize It is said that in the conditions of modern business and marketing in developing countries, where agriculture has a relatively large share in the economy, it is especially important to organize logistics lines.

Research methodology

In order to analyze the prospects of small agrologistics centers in the regions of Georgia, a mixed method of research was used, which includes both office and field research.

As part of the cabinet study, a review and analysis of the literature was performed. The discussion of Georgian literature mainly served to determine how much attention is focused on agrologistics in Georgia and what findings or researches have been conducted in this direction. And the review of foreign literature serves not only to discuss the current researches and achievements on a world scale, but also to adapt foreign examples and experiences to the Georgian reality.

As for the field research, it was conducted as a mixed research. Which means that both quantitative and qualitative research methods were used during the research. The goal of both of them was to present the perspectives of agrologistics centers in the reality of Georgia. However, the quantitative type of research, in

contrast to the qualitative one, was intended for a relatively wide audience and therefore reflects the perspectives of agrologistics centers from a different angle. Qualitative research included a small but targeted audience, which allowed us to see not only the perspectives, but also the pros and cons, as well as the impact of agrologistics centers on the agricultural sector.

The target audience for quantitative research, as mentioned, included a relatively broad target population, namely farmers, entrepreneurs and representatives of agricultural services. Based on the responses of the interested parties, it is possible to discuss how the society will receive agro-logistics centers and how positively it will be met. During the quantitative research, a questionnaire was drawn up and the target groups were interviewed through this questionnaire. A semi-structured questionnaire was developed, which included open and closed questions about the field of activity, region, export potential and agro-logistics centers. The questionnaire was sent electronically via Google Form. The survey was conducted in compliance with ethical norms. In total, 125 respondents took part in the research.

As for qualitative research, in this case in-depth interviews were conducted with specialists and experts in various fields. Interviews lasted 1.5 - 2 hours, recording and further analysis took place. The purpose of in-depth interviews is to present the positive aspects of agrologistics centers from different angles, to identify challenges, hindering factors and negative aspects. Acquaintance and analysis of opinions from different perspectives on the optimal agrologistics center model for the reality of Georgia.

Research results - quantitative research

Quantitative research, as mentioned above, included a survey of the community employed in agriculture through a questionnaire. The purpose of this was to understand the attitude of society towards agrologistic centers. The questionnaire consisted of ten closed questions. The first five questions are relatively informative and serve to understand the respondent's field of activity, region and similar issues. And the other five questions were aimed at understanding the attitude of the society directly to the agrologistics center. The first question served to understand in which field the respondent is employed. It was found that 70.3% of the interviewees were employed in primary production, 8.1-8.1% in agrotourism and processing of agricultural products, 10.8% in agricultural services, and the rest were distributed to other people, including representatives of non-governmental organizations.

From the second question, it is possible to understand which activity the interviewee is engaged in, livestock, poultry, production of their products, or growing of perennial or annual crops. It was found that the largest part of the research participants, 45.9%, produces annual crops, 32.4-32.4% pursues the cultivation of perennial crops in the production of livestock products, the activity of 13.5% is related to animal husbandry, and the least 5.4% is related to poultry farming. , and the rest was distributed in other directions. The fourth question concerns the duration of agriculture-related activities (see Figure 1).

Diagram #1

It was found that 27% of the respondents are engaged in the mentioned activity for a period of one to three years, 28% of the respondents consider a period of three to five years, and 10-10% are involved in the

agricultural field for a period of five to ten years or less than one year. The next question concerns the respondents'/farmers' interest in exporting (see Figure 2).

Diagram #2

It is especially noteworthy that 51% of the respondents do not intend to export, 24% cannot produce products of the appropriate quality or quantity, 17% intend to export in the near future, and 3% were exporters in the past, but now cannot export due to a number of reasons. As for the respondents who are currently engaged in the export of agricultural products, only 5% of the respondents were found to be such.

The following questions are devoted to understanding the public opinion regarding agrologistics centers. Specifically, the purpose of this question is to understand to what extent the interviewees agree with the idea that the creation of agro-logistics centers in the regions will contribute to the export of products (see diagram 3).

Diagram #3

As a result of the research, it is revealed that the absolute majority of respondents - 83% share the opinion that agro-logistics centers will promote export, 12%

partially agree with this opinion, and only 5% of respondents disagree. At the next stage of the research, the respondents assessed the importance of agrologistics centers (see diagram 4).

Diagram #4

As the results show, about 67% evaluate the usefulness of agrologistics centers with 8, 9 or 10 points. And below 8 points, 7 to 1 votes are almost evenly distributed, with a percentage of 2.4% to 7.1% for each.

According to the next question, the respondents had to express their opinion on what the creation of agrologistics centers will help the most: the growth of exports; raising the productivity of farmers' labor; production of competitive, quality products; if supporting agrotourism (diagram 5).

Diagram #5

According to the results, 46% of the respondents think that agrologistics centers will contribute to the production of quality and competitive products the most. 34% believe that these centers will increase the labor productivity of farmers; In the opinion of 17%, it will contribute to the growth of exports the most, while

only 3% see the potential positive impact of agro-logistics centers on the support of agro-tourism.

It was interesting to understand what the public thinks about the issue of who should be under the authority of the agrologistics center: the state, a private person, or a hybrid model (see diagram 6).

Diagram #6

Regarding this question, the opinion of the respondents is diverse. In particular, 29% think that the agrologistics center should be under the authority of the state; 28% prefer a private person. 19% believe that it would be better for agrologistics centers to be under the management of a private person who will be under the strict control of the state. According to 16.7%, it would be better for the state to manage this at the first stage, and then for a private person to take over. 7.1% of respondents found it difficult to answer this question and have no vision regarding the management model of agrologistics centers.

Research results - qualitative research

In the qualitative research, in-depth interviews were conducted with 12 respondents and they expressed their own opinion regarding agro-logistics centers based on their field of activity. The results show that in some issues the opinions are contradictory, while in others they completely coincide.

To the first basic question, whether it is necessary to create agrologistics centers in the regions of Georgia, the answer of all of them is positive, although they are substantiated with different arguments by specialists in different fields. According to the DCFTA expert, agrologistics centers will be particularly beneficial for stable supply of products to the foreign market and will facilitate the sale of products on foreign markets. From the logistic point of view, by creating agro-logistic centers, the necessary quantity for logistic operations will be collected. Experts in the field of agronomy said that coordination of farmers will be facilitated and production will become more orderly after the creation of agrologistics centers, which implies that agrotechnical operations of maintenance and harvesting of agricultural crops in farms will be properly planned. From an agro-economic point of view, since the most problematic issue in the agricultural value chain is the regulation of logistics lines, economists believe that the solution to this is to create a model of agro-logistics centers that will have a systemic advantage and will play a key role in the regulation of the supply chain in the field of agriculture. It was also argued that the creation of agro-

logistics centers will help to create a common integrated business-commercial base and to establish a logistics chain that will be focused on local and international markets. In addition, as the agro-engineer noted, the creation of similar centers will facilitate the introduction of high-tech operational systems in agriculture. As for the general public opinion on this issue, it absolutely coincides with the opinions of experts. The majority of respondents, 66.7%, evaluate the usefulness of agrologistics centers with 8, 9 and 10 points on a ten-point scale. In the end, emerging from the mentioned arguments, it can be said with certainty that the creation of agrologistics centers will be a positive event, both from an agronomic, economic, marketing and social point of view.

Regarding the negative sides of the agro-logistic centers, several opinions were actually expressed that were sharply different from each other. During one of the interviews, it was discussed that if there is one agrologistics center, there may be monopolization of both prices and services. In addition, the creation of agrologistics centers will make local products more competitive, and therefore, on the one hand, it will intensify the competition of importers, on the other hand, it will increase the consumer prices of agricultural products, which in turn is a positive event for farmers, but a negative event for consumers.

Answers obtained as a result of interviews about the structural units of the agrologistics center complement each other and finally allow the formation of a certain optimal model. However, it should be noted here that the expert in the field of logistics does not support the existence of such a structural unit in the agrologistics center, which will be related to the services of agronomic measures. Also, from the logistical point of view, the fact of purchase and subsequent sale of products from farmers by similar centers was negatively evaluated. As for structural units, in addition to the following structural units: warehouse, packaging, transport park, technopark, laboratory, storage, special emphasis was placed on the presence of a three-mode refrigeration unit and a ring performing information and analytical functions, which represents the so-called

brain of the center and whose functions will be marketing, processing of economic, logistics operations planning and management measures at the tactical and strategic level.

The question of which products and which regions the agrologistics center can be targeted at did not cause a great difference of opinion. The answer for the most part was that it could be done in every region depending on the culture. That is, in a specific region, it should be focused on the culture that is most promising in the given region. There was also an opinion that, taking into account the modern foreign experience, it would be better to have agrologistic centers focused on one product or one type of products.

Opinions about who should be under the authority of the agrologistics center were divided into two with respective arguments. Those who agreed with the management of the agrologistics center by the private sector cited the fact that the risks of monopoly would be too high in the case of state management. And those who preferred the agrologistics center to be under the control of the state said that in this case the systematization and coordination of the agrologistics centers would have more prospects. As for the intermediate position, it meant public-private partnership. Based on the results of the research, it can be said that the mentioned form of governance will be the most optimal for the healthy functioning of agrologistics centers.

During the interviews, the challenges and hindering factors that might threaten the creation or operation of agrologistics centers were identified. During the interviews, almost all respondents mentioned the lack of qualified personnel, which is likely to be one of the main challenges for such centers. In addition, it was said that it would be difficult to raise funds, as well as to convince the private sector to invest in such centers (Charaia et al., 2020; 2022; Lashkhi, Charaia 2017). It will also be difficult to inform the public correctly depending on their mentality and awareness. There is also a risk that the production will not be able to reach the logistics center, that is, it may not be able to produce the required amount. That is why it is necessary for the agrologistics center to develop synchronously with agriculture.

Conclusion and recommendations

The main challenge for the entry of agricultural products into the European Union single market is to ensure continuous supply of homogeneous products. Especially for developing countries with weak economies, it is especially important to create units in the agricultural sector that carry the functions of supply chain management. As a result of the survey, it was shown how much the society is interested in such centers and how positive it is. Based on the interviews with specialists in different fields, it became clear how the agrologistics center can be reflected in different fields.

As for the quantitative research, the majority of entrepreneurs in Georgia pursue primary production, which is not very profitable. It also appeared that a large part of society does not even think about exporting products. Based on the research, 51% of the respondents categorically exclude export, and more than 24%

cannot produce products of the required quality or quantity for export. Therefore, we can think that for about 75% of farmers, export is not even considered.

During the work on each part of the research, it was determined what form the agrologistics center should have in Georgia and what prerequisites it should meet. Finally, we can conclude that:

- For the development of Georgia's agriculture and the order of logistics lines in this sector, agro-logistics centers need to have a systematic form. These centers should be the link in agriculture through which strategic and tactical decisions will be made at the regional level.

- Logistics centers should provide farmers not only with logistics services (warehousing and transportation), but also with agronomic, marketing, economic and technical services.

- Logistics centers can be located in all regions. Depending on the region, it should be specialized only on one type of product or group of products.

- The logistics center may be given special importance in terms of creating stocks of strategic products at the state level.

- In order to convince farmers of the importance and benefits of agrologistics centers, it is necessary to conduct the right campaign and inform them correctly.

- Beneficiary of such centers should be voluntary for farmers. And in the case of cooperation, an appropriate contract must be signed between the agrologistics center and the farmer.

- The agro-logistic center should be able to provide services as well as purchase and then sell products from farmers, subject to certain conditions.

- Agrologistic centers need to establish contracts and relevant agreements with both export and local market representatives.

- In order to avoid monopolization and at the same time to preserve the system, it is necessary to create and manage an agrologistics center within the framework of public-private partnership, during which the rights and duties will be distributed between the state and the private sector.

- Existing storage farms can be used as a starting base for creating agrologistics centers.

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